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Software Management Plan

Version 2022

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Software Management Plan Template

Open Science, software quality, and software sustainability are key elements in eScience Center projects. They enable verification, reproducibility, and transparency in all phases of the research process, and maximize the chance for adoption, reuse and impact of software created in the projects.

Our Research Software Engineers put substantial effort into creating open, high-quality, and sustainable software. For example, to allow community contributions and adoption of the software by others, all software will use permissive open-source licenses (research software developed by the eScience Center will be licensed under the Apache 2.0 license) and source code will be published in publicly accessible repositories such as GitHub from the start of the project.

In addition, software will be made to adhere to the FAIR software recommendations¹ and be made available in the Research Software Directory². This ensures a basic level of software quality, makes the software findable for search engines, enables software citation, and adds relevant metadata such as documentation, related projects, tools and publications.

The long-term sustainability of the software developed in eScience Center projects is the responsibility of the Lead Applicant. This template should be used to describe the measures that will be taken, both during and after the project, to ensure the usability and availability of the software beyond the duration of the project itself. These measures may be taken directly by the Lead Applicant, project partners, or their institutes, but may also involve external organizations or communities.

The questions that follow should be interpreted in the broadest sense, as there is no one-size-fits-all solution for long-term software sustainability. However, each of the measures must be described as concretely as possible. In each case it should be specified which action will be taken at which moment; likewise, in each case it should be made clear with whom or with which institute the responsibility for ensuring sustainability lies. Note that this document should be signed by the authorized signatory of the institute responsible for carrying out this Software Management Plan. If multiple institutes are involved in this plan, then each should provide a signature.

¹ <https://fair-software.nl>

² <https://software.esciencecenter.nl>

1. What measures will be taken during the project to ensure the long-term sustainability of the software developed in the project? (max. 300 words)

[Your answer here]

Some examples include:

- *A researcher or RSE from a research institute is allocated to the project to co-develop the software during the project and help maintain it afterwards.*
- *A community will co-develop the software and help maintain it afterwards.*
- *Organizing workshops and hands-on user training to create or extend a community around the software.*
- *The software will be developed as part of an overarching software suite used in other (research) projects.*
- *A commercial partner interested in exploiting the software is included as co-applicant on the basis of a concrete in-cash or in-kind investment.*

2. What measures will be taken to support the software after the duration of the project? (max. 300 words)

[Your answer here]

Some examples include:

- *The software is hosted by an institute and a user support desk is made available for a certain period.*
- *The software is integrated into teaching in a course on the Bachelor or Master level*
- *The software is integrated into a research infrastructure based on a large community.*
- *A commercial partner or spin-off will continue the support and development of the software.*

3. What resources are needed to ensure the long-term usability and availability of the software, and how will these resources be funded or obtained? (max. 300 words)

[Your answer here]

Some examples include:

- *Storage or compute infrastructure needed to host the software.*
- *RSEs needed to maintain the software and support the community that uses it.*
- *A user support desk.*

4. Are there other measures that will be taken to promote the software's longevity? (max. 300 words)

[Your answer here]

Some examples include:

- *Additional project proposals which will help to further develop the software.*
- *Outreach through mainstream media such as newspaper articles, blogs, YouTube videos, tweets, etc.*

5. Signature

The institute(s) will ensure that this Software Management Plan is carried out as specified above.

Authorized signatory³:

Institute:

Name:

Date:

Signature:

(please copy this section if needed)

³ An authorized signatory is a person who may be held ultimately responsible on behalf of a research institute or other legal entity.

Examples include, but are not limited to:

- dean of faculty
- institute director
- head of research infrastructure